

Harmful algal blooms along central Guatemalan Pacific coast

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Abstract

Along the Guatemalan Pacific coast, sporadic studies on harmful algal blooms (HAB) date back to 1987 when 193 human intoxications (including 22 deaths) caused by the dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense* were reported. In recent years, HAB in the study zone have been caused by *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* and *P. bahamense*; however, the reports do not mention accompanying species. To fill this gap, studies on phytoplankton and its spatial-temporal changes in relation to physical-chemical variables were initiated. In November 2019, *P. bahamense* reached an abundance of 1.00×10^4 cells L⁻¹. In September 2020, *M. polykrikoides* vegetative cells reached 1.24×10^6 cells L⁻¹ and its cysts 1.53×10^6 cells L⁻¹. *Noctiluca scintillans* bloomed in November 2020 and March 2021 (up to 1.20×10^6 cells L⁻¹). Since January 2021, monthly monitoring has been launched at three sampling stations with site depths from 1.5 to 5 m at 3-5 km from the coastline. In March 2021, a *M. polykrikoides* bloom was detected (1.20×10^6 cells L⁻¹). Yearly monitoring allowed us to follow seasonal changes in both harmful species and the entire phytoplankton community; this is recommended for considering when studying a bloom event.

Keywords: Guatemala, harmful algal blooms, *Margalefidinium*, Pacific, *Pyrodinium*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7032902>

Introduction

Plankton studies in Guatemala are associated with the history of algal blooms due to poisoning problems in humans that occurred in August 1987, when 193 intoxications due to shellfish consumption were reported on the Pacific coast of Guatemala, of which 22 cases were fatal (Rosales *et al.*, 1989). *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* was the causative agent that produced a paralytic toxin. The species was reported again as blooming in November 2019 in coastal waters of Guatemala's Pacific (Paz-Cordón, 1997). The main objective of this study was to contribute to the knowledge of phytoplankton diversity, distribution and abundance and its relationship with the physico-chemical variables in Guatemala's Pacific.

Material and Methods

The sampling zone was located at Puerto Quetzal, in the area of the submarine San José Canyon, which cuts the continental slope perpendicularly and runs into the Mesoamerican Trench, near the sediment plumes of the Achiguate and María Linda rivers (Fig. 1).

Monthly monitoring was performed from January to May 2021 in the morning between 8:00 and 12:00. Phytoplankton was collected from three sites (at the Texaco, Entre Morros and Recalada navigation buoys) from 1.5 m and 5 m depths using a 6.4 L Van Dorn water bottle. Additionally, horizontal surface tows were taken for 5 min at each station with a hand net of 25 μ m mesh size. The samples were fixed with acid Lugol solution and stored in 500 mL Kimax-Kimble glass bottles in a cooler. Transparency was measured with

a Secchi disk. Surface water temperature, dissolved oxygen, conductivity and salinity were measured and recorded using a HANNA HI-98194 multiparameter meter.

Fig. 1. Phytoplankton sampling sites at three navigation buoys from January to May 2021.

In the laboratory, total dissolved solids (TDS), phosphorus, ammonium, total nitrogen, sulphates and chlorophyll-*a* were measured by the absorbance technique using prepared solutions and calibration curves. Phytoplankton cells were counted under an Olympus CKX41 inverted microscope using the Utermöhl technique after sedimentation in 50 mL cylinders. To determine the differences in abundance between months and sampling site, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test and a one-way ANOVA analysis were applied. To elaborate the species-accumulation curve the program EstimateS (version 9.1.0) and non-parametric estimators Chao 1 and ACE (Abundance-based Coverage Estimator) were used.

In addition, from October to November 2019, bivalves were collected for saxitoxin determination using a mouse bioassay at the National Laboratory of Health in cooperation

with the Directorate of Normativity of Fishery and Aquaculture of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Food (MAGA in Spanish) of Guatemala. These bloom events were observed by the Guatemala National Commission of Red Tide Studies. Saxitoxin concentration was determined by the AOAC official method 959.08.16.

Results and Discussion

The site depths varied between 20 m and 30 m, and bottom sediments were limesand (Entre Morros and Recalada buoys) or sand (Texaco buoy). During the study period the mean surface water temperature was 28.79 °C (ranging from 27.77 to 30.72), the mean salinity was 33.67 (ranging from 33.15 to 33.76) and the mean transparency was 23.37 m (from 5 to 35 m).

Cyanobacteria contributed up to 46% in terms of abundance, mainly due to *Trichodesmium erythraeum*. From January to February it was one of the dominant species in net samples. Dinoflagellates were the most abundant (71%) during the study period, followed by diatoms (23%). Among other major taxonomic groups, cyanobacteria were most important, contributing about half in terms of abundance, mainly represented by the filamentous colonial *T. erythraeum*. Among dinoflagellates, at the level of order, the Gymnodiniales predominated in abundance (56%), mainly due to *Akashiwo sanguinea* and *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* (both vegetative cells and cysts), followed by the Gonyaulacales (33%), Peridiniales (6%), Prorocentrales (3%), Dinophysiales and Noctilucales (1% each). The diatoms from the order Thalassiosirales were the most abundant (Table 1), mainly represented by

Lauderia annulata, *Planktoniella sol* and *Skeletonema tropicum*.

Table 1. Mean abundances of planktonic diatoms at the order level in the central Guatemalan Pacific from January to May 2021.

Order	Mean abundance (cells L ⁻¹)
Bacillariales	19.47
Biddulphiales	2.72
Briggerales	1.96
Chaetocerotales	11.33
Coscinodiscales	8.07
Eupodiscales	2.52
Hemiaulales	0.47
Lithodesmiales	0.56
Melosirales	1.40
Naviculales	7.14
Rhaphoneidales	1.40
Rhizosoleniales	9.44
Stephanopyxales	1.87
Thalassionematales	2.24
Thalassiosirales	30.20

No significant differences in phytoplankton abundances occurred between sampling sites or between the two sampling depths at each site (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 0.6742$); however, there were significant differences between months ($p = 0.004$). No significant differences in species richness between sampling sites or months were observed (ANOVA, $p = 0.3056$).

In March 2021, high phytoplankton abundances occurred at Entre Morros and Recalada buoys at the entrance to Port

Quetzal. It is a hydrodynamically active area influenced by currents produced by ships that also resuspend bottom sediments forming sand banks.

In general, both the highest species richness and abundance were found at 1.5 m depth. The Simpson index varied inversely with heterogeneity: the index values decrease or increase according to the increase or decrease in diversity, respectively. The index of dominance overestimates the role of the most abundant species at each sampling site, which allowed us to observe a very close relationship (in terms of physico-chemical variables, species richness and cell abundance) between Entre Morros and Recalada buoys. Pielou's equitability index was highest at the Texaco buoy at 1.5 m depth, where *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp., *S. tropicum* and *M. polykrikoides* cysts dominated. This sampling site is located closer to the Achiguat River and further from the port operations than other sites. River runoff increased during the study period under the influence of the El Niño-Southern Oscillation phenomenon; this may have resulted from the above average rainfall.

The Bray-Curtis dissimilarity in cell abundance between sampling sites and sampled depths (in total, six) revealed two groups (Fig. 2): (1) the Entre Morros and Recalada buoys, and (2) the Texaco buoy.

Hitherto, the species richness from the three sampling sites reached 111; however, after five monthly surveys it has not reached an asymptote although the database includes 8,784 species records.

During October and November 2019, blooming planktonic microalgae were

sampled at the Entre Morros and Recalada buoys and counted in a 1 mL Sedgwick-Rafter chamber. In October 2019, *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* reached 3.90×10^4 cells L^{-1} , and saxitoxin concentration reached 3,275 MU 100 g^{-1} . Cell abundances and saxitoxin concentrations were 3,037 MU 100 g^{-1} and 1.01×10^4 cells L^{-1} on November 7, and 5,200 MU 100 g^{-1} and 3.90×10^4 cells L^{-1} on November 22, respectively (saxitoxin concentration is given in mouse units per 100 g of bivalve mollusc flesh). Historically, *M. polykrikoides* vegetative cells and cysts and *P. bahamense* var. *compressum* have caused blooms in the central Guatemalan Pacific. In November 2020, a *Noctiluca scintillans* bloom was reported in the marina of the Port of Quetzal, and for the first time for the study area the abundance of this species was estimated; *N. scintillans* was observed again in March 2021.

Fig. 2. Bray-Curtis dissimilarity in cell abundance between sampling sites (three) and sampled depths (two per site: 1.5 m and 5 m); Rec: Recalada, EM: Entre Morros, Tex: Texaco.

Although the monitoring of harmful phytoplanktonic species has been focused on a few critical species, it should be continued in the framework of phytoplankton monitoring in general to trace any blooms caused by other species. Inter-institutional collaboration continues to be an important way to obtain meaningful results.

Acknowledgements. The monitoring was performed within the framework of the project “Strengthening capacities in marine and coastal environments using nuclear and isotopic techniques” (RLA 7025; financed by the International Atomic Energy Agency through the Network of Studies on Marine-Coastal Stressors of the Latin America and Caribbean (REMARCO in Spanish); local coordinator on a harmful algal stressor: KEPC). The study was possible due to the collaboration between CEMA-USAC, the Department of Observation and Marine Research (OBIMAR in Spanish) of the Quetzal Port Company and the Pacific Naval Command of Guatemala

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